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Thermoeconomic evaluation of boiler feedwater heating and deaeration

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Introduction

Boiler feed water deaeration by direct steam contact heating is a common practice for removal of non condensable gases from boiler feed water which otherwise would cause corrosion of heat exchange surfaces and would lessen the corresponding overall heat transfer coefficients. There are many factors influencing the choice of deaeration temperature and optional subsequent feed water heating, such as type of fuel used, boiler design, stack temperature, type of industry (with or without steam turbine) and more. For example small industries without steam turbine prefer to deaerate the boiler feed water at 102 to 105 °C, which is the lower deaeration temperature limit, to ensure both low internal steam consumption and low stack losses. For bigger industries, instead, equipped either with condensing or backpressure steam turbine, it is usual to deaerate at higher temperatures [1-3] (corresponding to the pressure of the process steam used) and to employ additional feed water heating by condensing intermediate pressure steam, which is favorable from thermodynamical point of view. Big steam power plants with condensing turbines employ a number of low pressure feed water heaters as well as a number of high pressure feed water heaters, preheating the feed water even to 250 °C [4-7] in order to maximize their electric efficiency. On the other hand, combined gas and steam turbine plants deaerate at 102 to 105 °C and employ no additional feed water heating [8,9], since the corresponding stack loss increase outweighs the gain in electric efficiency.

As one can imagine, the choice of optimal feed water heating is even more complicated when retrofitting an existing industry, since on the one hand there usually are additional constraints and obstacles and on the other one retrofit solution is tailor-made for each industry, which implies a big number of difficulties as well as a number of possible solutions to be carefully considered. Application of thermoeconomic analysis is not as straightforward as in design calculations, because of diurnal as well as seasonal changes in operational parameters; frequently a retrofit has to rely more on an advice from an experienced engineer [7] than on rigorous computation. Furthermore, the aim of retrofit is not to find the best solution, but to find a good solution relatively quickly, without too much saving potential lost [10] and with acceptable investment cost ensuring a good payback period [11]. Therefore, instead to put too much effort in developing and applying advanced software, simpler calculations and heuristic rules combined with some serious economic considerations might prove to be a good way in meeting retrofit targets.

Based on the concept mentioned above, results of simplified thermoeconomic analysis will be the source data for some considerations and simple solutions, which may be directly used by engineers when improving the feed water heating and deaeration system.

Practical considerations

In most industrial cases, condensate return temperature is less than 100 °C, often less than 70 °C, because of inevitable heat losses and because of allowing the pressurized condensates to expand to atmospheric pressure in the condensate collection tanks. Furthermore, condensate return is always smaller than 100 % and the loss has to be compensated with fresh chemically treated water. Thus, even for basic deaeration at 102 °C, some low pressure has to be used in deaerator, being the internal steam consumption of boiler station. Smaller industries aren't usually equipped with steam turbine and their aim is to keep the internal steam consumption as low as possible, usually preheating the condensates with flue gases (or with some other suitable hot stream with heat capacity large enough to accomplish a notable temperature rise of condensates) prior to deaeration and adopting deaeration temperature usually lower than 110 °C.

Large industries, on the other hand, usually have at least one backpressure steam turbine, or possibly a condensing one with one or more extractions, which allows them to employ additional feed water heating to even more than 200 °C. Since they usually consume more electricity than they produce, optimal feed water heating, which increases the amount of electricity produced from the same amount of fuel, is for them an interesting option how to decrease their energy bills. However, optimal feed water heating is always a tradeoff between increased electricity production and increased stack losses and it depends on many factors including live steam parameters, low- and intermediate pressure steam availability, type of fuel used in boiler (and thus boiler thermal efficiency and fuel price), type of steam turbine (backpressure or condensing) and many more. Since many of these factors may vary compared to designed state, designed feed water temperature is not always the optimal one, especially in older industries.

Effect of fuel type (and boiler type as well) is shown in composite curves in **Fig. 1,2**.

Fig. 1 a,b Composite curves of a conventional natural gas boiler (a) and a heat recovery steam generator (b), both generating 6 MPa / 440 °C steam

The first boiler type is a classical, natural gas – fired boiler with firing temperature of 2000 °C. The pinch is located at the end of economizer (= at the boiler outlet), which is a favorable situation for extensive feed water heating. Due to increased internal steam consumption, the total amount of steam generated in the boiler will increase as well, with only a small increase in fuel consumption covering the increased stack losses and the surplus of heat converted additionally into electricity. The second one is a single-pressure heat recovery steam generator which utilizes hot

exhaust gas from a gas turbine to raise high pressure steam. In this case, the pinch is located at the end of evaporator, which means that feed water temperature has only limited effect on steam generation rate. For this type of boiler, additional feed water heating above the deaeration temperature just significantly increases stack losses without increasing steam generation rate and is therefore unfavorable.

Majority of other fuel and boiler types lies within these two situations, including large coal and oil fired steam generators with usual feed water preheating above 200 °C and large biomass fired steam generators employing feed water temperature up to 150 – 200 °C.

Number of feed water heaters varies according to the size of industry and according to steam levels available. While up to four feed water heaters are applied in steam power plants, just one feed water heater is present in average sized industry, often being the deaerator itself (feed water is deaerated at higher temperatures).

Retrofit of feed water heating temperatures

Retrofit of feed water temperatures must take into consideration additional constraints and possible solutions. As an example: stack temperature decreases with decreasing boiler load. For each type of fuel used, there exists some minimal stack temperature to avoid condensation of water in stack and resulting stack corrosion. If stack temperature is near this limit at higher boiler loads (thus improving boiler thermal efficiency), feed water temperature has to be increased at low boiler loads. This is possible only if feed water temperature has been kept below the temperature achievable by given steam pressure, which is an unfavorable situation considering electricity production on steam turbine.

Generally, possible solutions for feed water temperature retrofit are:

1. Increasing feed water temperature to the level achievable by steam pressure available./ Decreasing steam pressure level. Calculations have to be made, if the gain in electricity production outweighs increased stack losses, since more fuel has to be combusted to ensure enough steam for technology. If justified economically and if an intermediate pressure steam is available, additional feed water heater can be installed, further raising the feed water temperature by 20 to 40 °C. Decreasing the overall steam pressure level is limited by technology demands as well as by the range of steam pressures which can be supplied by the steam turbine.
2. Decreasing steam pressure just for feed water heating by making use of simple steam turbines or steam motors. Nowadays, simple steam turbines are available with outputs as low as 100 kW_e and isentropic expansion efficiency of up to 60 %. Their simple construction enables their price – around 20 mil. Sk per 1 MW installed power output – to be low enough to promise a good pay back period in industrial applications. Producers of steam motors claim the steam motors to maintain nearly the same isentropic efficiency at part loads, thus surpassing that of simple steam turbines which quickly deteriorates with decreasing load, but the references about employing steam motors in industry are scarce. Both simple steam turbine and steam motor increase the electricity production in given industry nearly without affecting the amount of fuel to be combusted, thus being an interesting option where fuel is expensive and/or of limited amount.
3. If both 1. and 2. aren't feasible, waste heat streams (if available) can be used to preheat feed water in a separate heat exchanger, whereby steam usage for further heating and deaeration can be decreased and thus the overall economics of feed water preparation improves. This measure can also be combined with 1. or 2.

Thermoeconomic analysis

Thermoeconomic analysis comprises both thermodynamic and economic analysis, but treats them separately, thus ensuring the thermodynamically interesting solutions being always economically viable. Thermodynamic analysis, often called second law analysis or exergetic analysis is based on simultaneous solution of material, enthalpic and exergetic balances for a chosen system. For a system without chemical reaction and without accumulation, they are given as follows:

$$\sum_i \dot{m}_i = \sum_j \dot{m}_j \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_i \dot{H}_i - \sum_j \dot{H}_j = -\dot{Q}_{in} + \dot{W}_{out} + \dot{H}_{lost} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_i \dot{E}_i - \sum_j \dot{E}_j = -\dot{E}_{Qin} + \dot{W}_{out} + \dot{I} \quad (3)$$

Indices i and j denote inlet, respectively outlet streams; \dot{m} , \dot{H} , \dot{E} stand for mass flow, enthalpy flow and exergy flow. \dot{Q}_{in} denotes heat input into the system and \dot{E}_{Qin} gives its corresponding exergy flow into the system. \dot{W}_{out} is useful work (mechanic, electric) extracted from the system; \dot{H}_{lost} stands for enthalpy losses into the surrounding and \dot{I} quantifies irreversibility (e.g. exergy destruction rate) and it includes both exergy flow corresponding to enthalpy losses and to exergy destruction caused by system irreversibility. Exergy of material streams is defined as follows:

$$\dot{E}_i = \dot{m}_i((h_i - h_0) + T_0(s_i - s_0)) \quad (4)$$

Index i denotes actual stream conditions and index 0 stands for environmental conditions; h is specific enthalpy and s is specific entropy. Useful work obtained from the system is treated as pure exergy flow. Exergy, a quantity of theoretically obtainable useful work if the system is brought into equilibrium with its surrounding, is a suitable measure of theoretical system performance. The aim of thermodynamic analysis is to minimize exergy destruction rate, regardless of the cost of measures taken to ensure it. Thus, by its nature, thermodynamic analysis itself can just locate the subsystems working with biggest irreversibility, but it is the aim of economic analysis to properly quantify the expenses accompanying irreversibility decrease and to promote measures which both substantially decrease the irreversibility and ensure a good pay back period.

Cost coefficients are assigned to irreversibility rates in economic analysis, thereby transferring the exergy losses into monetary units. Gains in irreversibility decrease are weighed against expenses connected with the improvement – investment costs, depreciation, maintenance costs etc. and a suitable economic criterion (simple pay back period, internal rate of return, annual savings...) is chosen to distinguish between viable and non viable options. It is often the case that viable solutions are simple as well, since the best solutions from thermodynamic point of view, despite their saving potential, require extensive reorganization and their realization may interrupt the production process for some time, which causes additional expenses to arise and in the end makes those solutions unacceptable.

Case study

The chosen industrial company has two feed water deaeration and heating systems, which could be considered for case study; water to be deaerated is supplied from central condensate collection tank. Feed water from system 1 is fed to a high pressure steam boiler B1 fired by biomass derived fuel with nominal production of 160 t/h 8 MPa/460 °C steam. Feed water from system 2 is

fed to two high pressure steam boilers both fired by biomass or biomass derived fuel and both producing 4 MPa/400 °C steam; boiler B2 has nominal steam output of 200 t/h steam; boiler B3 has nominal output of 110 t/h steam. Steam from B1 is fed to a backpressure steam turbine, which delivers process steam at 0,6 MPa. Steam from B2 and B3 is fed to two identical backpressure steam turbines with one extraction, delivering 1,3 and 0,6 MPa process steam. Part of the produced 0,6 MPa steam is used to deaerate and preheat the feed water; in system 1 to 117 °C and in system 2 up to 140 °C. A typical composite curve of one of the boilers is show in **Fig. 2**. It must stressed, that, on the whole, borders of superheater, evaporator and economizer in the composite curve diagram aren't exactly defined, since water at the economizer outlet is still undercooled (even by some tenths of degrees Centigrade) with respect to boiling temperature and wet steam leaves the evaporator. Furthermore, additional feed water is injected into superheated steam, in order to keep its final temperature at desired value.

Only the steam output of boiler B3 varies seasonally; steam outputs of B1 and B2 are not affected by actual season. However, water temperature to be deaerated varies with season, as well as does the feed water temperature for boilers B2 and B3, thus a good solution for optimal feed water heating and deaeration for B1 is easier to be found than that for B2 and B3. Therefore, in the first phase, only feed water heating and deaeration for boiler B1 was evaluated.

Fig. 2 Composite curve of boiler B1

Concerning the retrofit of feed water preparation for B1, deaeration temperature decrease was not allowed for the sake of keeping stack temperature above acid dew point. Calculation of 0,6 MPa steam consumption in the deaerator were based on enthalpic balance with a 2 % excess steam to cover the losses of steam in the deaerator exhaust – this approach was verified by corresponding steam consumption data. Heat losses from deaerator were disregarded, since it is a well insulated vessel. Further assumptions made are summed up in **Tab. 1**.

Boiler steam output, t/h	120
Water to be heated temperature, °C	75
0,6 MPa steam enthalpy, kJ/kg	2920
Produced steam enthalpy, kJ/kg	3300
Ambient conditions: Temperature, K	288
Enthalpy, kJ/kg	62,94
Entropy, kJ/kg/K	0,2243
Slope of backpressure steam turbine characteristics, kW/t/h	150
Simple steam turbine adiabatic efficiency at full load, %	65
Slope of simple steam turbine characteristics, kW/t/h	60
Price of heat in produced steam, Sk/GJ	200
Electricity price, Sk/MWh	3000
Working hours per year	7000

Tab. 1 Basic parameters and assumptions for the calculation

Further assumptions, always verified by accessible data, are based on following relations:

$$\eta_{boiler} = 0,82 \cdot (1 + 0,0007 \cdot (117 - t_{feed\ water})) \quad (5)$$

$$C_{steam\ turbine} = 8,1 \cdot \left(\frac{m_s}{10} \right)^{0,6} \quad (6)$$

Equation (5) denotes the deviation of B2 thermal efficiency with the change in feed water temperature and equation (6) expresses simple steam turbine cost in mil. Sk based on reference designed steam mass flow into deaerator (10 t/h) and steam mass flow m_s in the case of higher feed water temperature.

Our approach to retrofit of feed water temperature was based on combining feed water temperature increase and commissioning a simple steam turbine, since steam pressure of deaeration steam is given by technological demands. As explained above, increasing feed water temperature causes both boiler efficiency decrease (due to stack temperature increase) and specific heat consumption decrease (since less heat must be transferred in boiler into feed water to produce the same amount of steam). These two effects counteract and the resulting effect is strongly dependent on boiler construction, type of fuel combusted, undercooling of feed water at the exit of economizer and many more. For the given boiler it has been found that increasing feed water temperature up to 135 °C results in a subtle increase of steam output with the same mass flow of fuel combusted. Thus, additional fuel has to be combusted, in order to satisfy both steam demand in technology and increased steam consumption in deaerator. Simple steam turbine uses the available pressure difference between 0,6 MPa steam and steam pressure required to heat water in the deaerator to the desired temperature and converts the corresponding enthalpic difference into electric work. It can be thus expected, that both solutions may positively contribute to the steam cycle efficiency. The measure of their economic viability is the simple pay back period (PBP) and marginal electric efficiencies, defined as follows:

$$PBP = \frac{C_{steam\ turbine}}{(C_{a.e.} - C_{a.f.})} \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_{el, marg} = \frac{\Delta P_{el}}{\Delta Q_{fuel}} \quad (8)$$

Results and discussion

Based on equations (1-8) and parameters given in **Tab. 1**, feed water heating and deaeration was analyzed from energetic, thermodynamic and economic point of view. As expected, mass flow of steam into deaerator increases with increasing temperature in deaerator, as can be seen in **Fig. 3a**. The same holds true for irreversibility.

Situation is more interesting in power output of simple steam turbine designed for various steam mass flows and pressure differences, according to the deaeration temperature. **Fig. 3a** shows, that with increasing deaeration temperature, designed power output tends to decline after a short plateau. To explain this, one must consider two factors, which counteract when increasing deaeration temperature. One of them is increasing steam mass flow, to which the designed simple steam turbine power output is directly proportional. The other one is decreasing pressure difference, which estimates the available enthalpic difference and via steam adiabatic efficiency also real enthalpic difference for steam expansion. Available enthalpic difference decreases non-linearly. Clearly, at hypothetic deaeration temperature of 160 °C, which is the saturation temperature of 0,6 MPa steam, available pressure difference would be zero and thus power output as well. One can therefore expect that with increasing deaeration temperature, sooner or later the simple steam turbine power output decreases, which is exactly what can be seen in **Fig. 3a**.

Fig. 3a Steam mass flow into deaerator, irreversibility and designed power output of simple steam turbine as a function of deaeration temperature; **Fig. 3b** Specific cost of simple steam turbine and corresponding pay back period as a function of deaeration temperature.

Consequences of increasing steam mass flow through simple steam turbine and of decreasing power output can clearly be foreseen – steam turbine has to be larger, in order to accommodate

increased steam mass flow, which in turn causes its cost to increase. On the other hand, decreasing power output lessens the corresponding annual gain. These two factors cause the pay back period of simple steam turbine to rise quickly, making the corresponding investment opportunity less attractive, which is doubtless the case in **Fig. 3b**.

Fig. 4. Partial marginal electric efficiencies of both water temperature increase and simple steam turbine and their combined marginal electric efficiency as a function of deaeration temperature.

As mentioned above, combining deaeration temperature increase and simple steam turbine commissioning was chosen as an effective way to improve steam system performance. Boiler B2 exhibits a subtle steam production increase with increasing boiler feed water temperature, which enables extra electricity production on the corresponding backpressure steam turbine. To cover the increased steam demand for feed water heating and deaeration, extra fuel has to be combusted in B2. One can therefore calculate power output increase as a sum of extra power output and additional power output due to increased fuel combustion. According to (8), partial marginal electric efficiency of feed water temperature increase can be calculated. Similar procedure can be repeated with incorporation of simple steam turbine, whereby combined marginal efficiency of both feed water temperature increase and simple steam turbine incorporation can be obtained. By subtracting the values of feed water temperature increase from the values of combined solution and via (8) one arrives at partial marginal electric efficiency of simple steam turbine. This efficiency is purely hypothetical, since simple steam turbine operation at higher temperatures inevitably incorporates the effect of increased feed water temperature.

All three efficiencies are shown in **Fig 4** as a function of deaeration temperature. As can be seen, in our case study the combined marginal electric efficiency is superior to the partial marginal electric efficiency of deaeration temperature increase, but both of them are above 30 % which makes

them interesting compared to usual overall electric efficiency in a backpressure steam turbine plant system (around 15 %). Simple steam turbine incorporation is shown to be the cause for combined marginal electric efficiency increase.

However, increasing simple steam turbine cost with deaeration temperature increase indicates, that probably the most viable solution incorporates either zero or just subtle feed water temperature increase combined with simple steam turbine incorporation. Therefore, incorporating simple steam turbine with unchanged feed water temperature was chosen as a reference solution and sensitivity analysis has been carried out by changing the most important parameter – water temperature at the inlet of deaerator (this parameter is most likely to vary during the year). Results of sensitivity analysis are plotted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Pay back period (full symbols) and corresponding annual gain (open symbols) as a function of water temperature at the inlet of deaerator

The idea was to find out what happens, if water temperature deviates from the design value. It is obvious, that increasing inlet water temperature with other parameters unchanged decreases the steam consumption in deaerator, thus worsening the performance of simple steam turbine sized to accommodate higher steam mass flow. If one expects the inlet water temperature to vary between 75 and 90 °C, the most conservative solution is to size simple steam turbine to steam mass flow at 90 °C inlet temperature, which ensures constant annual gain as well as constant pay back period, quite acceptable for industrial companies. However, if average inlet water temperature stays below 80 °C, conservative solution brings about lower annual gain than steam turbine sized to lower inlet water temperatures. On the other hand, sizing the steam turbine to too low inlet temperatures may result in substantial power output loss and corresponding increase of pay back period, if the inlet temperature stays high for longer time.

Decreasing steam output of B2 has the same effect as increasing water temperature at the inlet of deaerator, which indicates, that it is smart to size the simple steam turbine to average steam output of B2 rather than to the full steam output as well as to average inlet water temperature rather than the lowest one; additional steam required to heat and deaerate the feed water can always be fed into deaerator through the simple steam turbine by-pass.

Conclusions

Feed water heating and deaeration is an important factor influencing combined heat and power efficiency. The way how to perform it varies according to the type of industry and often its technical state is far from being ideal, making it an attractive target for optimization. Rigorous thermoeconomic analysis is often too laborious and its results may not be substantially better than those of a simplified analysis. To prove it, we chose an industrial company, where we performed the retrofit of feed water heating and deaeration system. Its outcome is a combination of two simple solutions – increasing feed water temperature and commissioning a simple steam turbine to gain electric output from expanding steam consumed in deaerator. From economic point of view, though, it is better just to install steam turbine without increasing feed water temperature, as proved by marginal electric efficiencies and simple pay back period. When sizing the steam turbine, one has to consider the changes in water temperature at the inlet of deaerator, since they influence steam consumption in deaerator. Sensitivity analysis shows, that a certain under sizing may be acceptable, to ensure nearly full load performance through substantial part of year, whereby annual gain is more predictable and a short pay back period is achievable, which makes it more attractive for industrial application.

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